

EVORoadS

Evolutionary Solutions for Realising
a Holistic Safe System Approach
for All Road Users

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Project deliverable D6.2

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Meaning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LC	Lead Contact
ODI	Open Data Institute
STC	Scientific and Technical Committee
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EvoRoads project aims to accelerate the attainment of the Vision Zero EU goal. It intends to do so by providing models, tools, and services that enable a data-driven evolution of safety frameworks towards proactive safety risk warnings. The project will develop a multi-layered evolutionary safety assessment framework integrated into a safe mobility data space alongside analysis of all dimensions of the safe system approach to understanding unexplored correlations between safety and data from advanced infrastructure monitoring technologies. A federated platform will be realized to facilitate holistic monitoring of urban and rural road infrastructures, focusing on infrastructure deterioration and distress through the fusion of data from crowdsourcing and data and image sensors vertically ranging from road-bound to satellites. This platform will enable proactive road-user warnings and enhance road maintenance operations.

D6.2 is the EvoRoads project's Data Management Plan (DMP), which describes how data will be collected, stored, accessed, exchanged, made interoperable, and re-used. The DMP addresses the full data management approach for making research data FAIR (i.e., Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Through the definition and adoption of a comprehensive metadata profile, the DMP provides information on the control of research data, and how data will be handled and stored throughout the project's lifetime and beyond. Particular attention will be given to ethical issues dealing with the right to data protection, and the management of sensitive data.

As the DMP is meant to be a living document, this deliverable will be updated at M18 and M36.

Social Media link:

For further information please visit evoroads-project.eu

1 INTRODUCTION

The presented document consists of Deliverable D6.2 “Data Management Plan” which has been developed under WP6, “Project Management,” Task 6.4, “Responsible Innovation: Ethics Open Access and Data Management.”

The Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to introduce the essential aspects of the project's data management policy. It aims to provide a strategy for managing data generated and collected during the project and optimising access to and re-use of research data.

For each dataset used in EvoRoads, a metadata description is provided with a data summary, FAIR data, allocation of resources, data security, ethical aspects, and any other relevant aspect in managing the specific dataset.

The metadata profile used to collect information on the dataset is presented and described in the following sections of this document. As the DMP is meant to be a living document, D6.2 will be updated at M18 and M36.

The DMP details which data the EvoRoads project will manage and generate, how they will be exploited or made accessible for verification purposes and re-use, and how they will be preserved and curated. The DMP addresses the full data management approach. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, the DMP includes information on:

- the control of research data, both during and after the conclusion of the project;
- what type of information will be gathered, analysed or produced;
- which framework and guidelines will be used;
- whether data will be accessible to the general public;
- how data will be handled and stored throughout the project's lifetime and beyond.

1.1 MAPPING EVOROADS OUTPUTS

This section provides a mapping of EvoRoads Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

EVOROADS GA COMPONENT TITLE	EVOROADS GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			
D6.2 Data Management Plan	Data Management Plan: how data will be collected, stored, accessed, exchanged, and made interoperable, as well as how data approved for publication can be used by others.	Chapters 3,4	Chapter 3 provides a comprehensive metadata profile for dataset description covering general information, FAIR aspects, allocation of resources, and ethical aspects. Chapter 4 provides a preliminary list of datasets collected or generated by EvoRoads, described according to the metadata profile.

TASKS

<p>T6.4 Responsible Innovation: Ethics, Open Access and Data Management</p>	<p>Task 6.4 aims to monitor various activities within the project to ensure sensible developments at the ethical, open access and data management level, referred to as Responsible Research Innovation (RRI). Among them there are data ethics and data management.</p>	<p>Chapter 4</p>	<p>Chapter 4 provides a preliminary list of EvoRoads data covering general information, FAIR aspects, allocation of resources, and ethical aspects.</p>
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1.2 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND REPORT STRUCTURE

The document is divided into the following sections:

- Chapter 2 describes the approach used for defining the DMP of EvoRoads, detailing the requirements and providing a comprehensive overview of its structure.
- Chapter 3 describes the metadata profile defined and adopted by EvoRoads for the description of the dataset in the DMP.
- Chapter 4 provides a preliminary list of datasets collected or generated by EvoRoads, described according to the metadata profile.
- Chapter 5 outlines conclusions and future releases.

2 THE ADOPTED APPROACH

A DMP document is required to answer certain questions relating to different aspects of data, such as ethical aspects or adherence to FAIR principles. For Horizon Europe projects, these DMP requirements are expressed in the Data Management Plan template¹ provided by the European Union. This template is divided into several main aspects and sub-aspects that data described and reported in the DMP must adhere to. This is done by providing several questions that must be answered. Because of this, a fixed or agreed-upon structure for the DMP is not provided, as each project differs and, as such, requires minor or major adjustments to the description of data used within the project, i.e. *the metadata profile*.

Arriving at an effective metadata profile is a balancing act between conformance to the DMP template and ease of use within the project. The metadata profile must answer every question found in the DMP template, but it should do so by defining a reasonable number of clearly defined *metadata fields*, e.g. the provider of the data, usage of the data within the project, etc.

To produce such a metadata profile, we leveraged our experiences with DMPs in various previous projects and an analysis of commonly available online tools to produce DMPs, these being DMPonline² and Argos³.

DMPonline does not provide an explicit metadata profile but instead asks the questions found in the DMP template. While this guarantees conformance to the DMP template guidelines, it introduces the potential for confusion in how the questions are answered by different partners, as there is no guideline or intended way to answer a question. Surveying the publicly available⁴ DMPs produced with DMPonline, we can note that this leads to DMPs describing data and data processes in an unstructured and abstract manner. For example, the question “How will you manage any ethical issues?” posed in the Ethics and Legal compliance section can only be answered in general terms because the question does not refer to a *particular* dataset. This is because DMPonline, in the way it presents the DMP template questions, does not prompt users to specify the datasets that will be used in the project. While this may be acceptable for projects not dealing with large datasets, this is not true for a more “technical” project like EvoRoads. Datasets must be identified, as specific ethical or technical issues could arise in their re-use or creation. By explicitly defining what datasets are in use within the project, it is easier to coordinate data sharing and re-use and address specific partner requests for data.

In this regard, Argos differs from DMPonline as it expects datasets to be defined. Argos provides a “Horizon Template” for the description of data, which covers all the aspects of the DMP guidelines template. Because this Horizon template is necessarily general purpose, as it must be applicable across various Horizon projects, it lacks certain metadata fields useful within the EvoRoads project, both from a data management and coordination perspective and a more technical, hands-on point of view. For example, a metadata field that has been found to be useful for data management is that of “*data requirements*,” meaning a set of data needs that the project partners agree upon and can be assigned to specific datasets. This metadata field aims to answer the questions: “What can this data be used for within the project? What data needs does it answer to?” Having this information explicitly stated greatly aids in intra-project communication. As another example of a missing metadata field, the Argos Horizon template lacks a “schema” metadata attribute. For data processing purposes, it is often not enough to know the data format (CSV, XML, etc.), but the schema and the intended semantics of the data need to be specified. If a dataset pertains to spatial measurements, are the measurements expressed in meters (metric) or feet (imperial)? Depending on the data format this information cannot be expressed in the data itself, and so the data needs to be accompanied by a schema, i.e. the intended semantics of the data.

1 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

2 <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

3 <https://argos.openaire.eu/home>

4 https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/public_plans

Another important aspect of the DMP guidelines template is the implicit distinction between re-used and generated data. Different questions apply to these categories of data. For example, for data that needs to be generated, an important question is how it will be generated and what ethical problems such data collection might entail. For re-used data, from an ethical perspective, the problem is in using already existing data.

Having analysed the DMP guidelines template and two of the most widely used DMP creation tools, EvoRoads decided to create a comprehensive metadata profile (see Section 3) and tools to support the dataset description.

2.1 TOOLS FOR EDITING THE DMP

EvoRoads proposes a comprehensive metadata profile for describing re-used and generated datasets. For the first release of the DMP, the metadata profile has been presented and made available to project partners in the form of Google Sheets. This has been done to have an initial common medium used to gather feedback on the profile and to commonly address potential issues of the profile or points of discussion. However, the EvoRoads DMP is not intended to maintain this form throughout the project's lifespan. Indeed, as indicated in the EvoRoads' GA, we intend to make the DMP publicly available through, for example, the Argos platform. The Argos platform allows users to write DMPs by selecting already existing templates, but it potentially allows users to provide their own templates.

Custom templates cannot be added directly within the Argos platform. Instead, users can contact the Argos development team to request the addition of their custom template. When releasing the first version of the EvoRoads DMP, after contacting the Argos team, we did not receive from them clear guidelines on how to make the EvoRoads metadata profile available on their platform.

As decided and described in the GA we intend to move forward with the Argos platform. Should this not be possible due to any number of problems raised by the Argos team or technical issues in adapting the proposed EvoRoads metadata profile, we intend to evaluate the usage of the Knowledge Catalog and Governance (KCONG) framework⁵ as a fallback alternative.

Cefriel will make use of the internally developed KCONG, a customizable framework for the definition of a catalogue of digital assets. KCONG is implemented as a digital platform that can be published online and accessed by users via a web browser. Different digital asset types can be defined in KCONG, and each type can be characterized by specifying a metadata descriptor, i.e., a set of information that a user interacting with the catalogue can insert/visualize for an asset of that type. KCONG offers programmatic access to the list of assets published and their metadata. Metadata can be serialized in RDF, enabling advanced functionalities based on querying and/or automated processing by agents of such metadata (e.g., in federation scenarios). Moreover, KCONG enables the definition of customizable processes for the governance of digital assets. The BPMN formalism⁶ is exploited to let users configure different governance processes for the lifecycle of digital assets.

For EvoRoads, the digital assets catalogued in KCONG would be the various datasets identified as relevant to the project and described using the EvoRoads metadata profile. An extension to KCONG that would automatically allow users to export managed assets to a DMP is under development. To comply with the GA where EvoRoads promised to make the DMP publicly available, the DMP exported from KCONG will be published on Zenodo⁷ or an equivalent open science portal.

⁵ <https://kcong.cefrriel.com/>

⁶ <https://www.bpmn.org/>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

3 THE EVOROADS METADATA PROFILE

This section describes the metadata profile defined and adopted in EvoRoads to structure the DMP, support the management of data generated and collected during the project, and optimise access to and re-use of research data.

A reference table has been defined to collect these metadata, and it is described in the following paragraphs according to the identified sections: general information, data summary, FAIR data, other research outputs, allocation of resources, ethical aspects, and other issues.

3.1 GENERAL INFORMATION AND DATA SUMMARY

This section provides an overview of the section of the EvoRoads metadata profile (see Table 2) used to collect general information about each dataset, including its identification, relation to the project, and data summary.

The first part of the information collected requires a dataset ID, which is assigned by EvoRoads after the initial data collection phase, a name to identify the dataset, a description of the dataset, and the partners responsible for collecting and managing the data (researcher’s name). Moreover, it collects information on the category the dataset belongs to (e.g., VRU, Vehicle, Safety, Traffic, Infrastructure, Connectivity) and the data requirements it fulfils (e.g., road user behavior, driving behavior, road traffic, road defects).

The section “Relation to the project” supports the specification of the workstream (detailed at the task level) and the work packages in which the described dataset is involved.

The third part of the information collected provides a summary of the dataset, including fields such as the purpose of the data, its schema and format, size, the license for the metadata describing the dataset, and the type of license considered. Moreover, it defines where the data is stored and the value of the dataset both from the project’s perspective and beyond the project’s lifetime.

A distinction is made between re-used datasets, for which the source of the re-used data is required, and generated datasets, for which the data generation process needs to be specified.

Finally, information on available data samples and the reference to project safety KPI(s) the dataset addresses are provided.

The fields are described in Table 2.

Table 2: “General Information and Data Summary” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

DATASET ID	<i>Cefriel will assign a unique dataset number after the initial data collection phase.</i>
DATASET name	<i><name></i>
Description	<i>Description of the dataset</i>
Category (Type of output)	<i>Basic categorization</i>
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	<i>What project data requirements the dataset address</i>
Partners	<i>Full name(s) of the researcher(s) responsible for the data within the project</i>
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	<i>Tx.y, Tz.k</i>
Work packages	<i>What work packages will use/intend to use this dataset WP x, WP y</i>
DATA SUMMARY	

Purpose of the data	<i>A description of the overall activities involving the specific dataset is expected. This should include detailed information on tasks and deliverables whenever possible.</i>
Schema of the data	<i>Schema of the data. Examples: GTFS, SIRI ...</i>
Format of the data	<i>Format of the data Examples: CSV, XML ...</i>
Size	<i>Estimated size of the dataset</i>
Dataset metadata license	<i>License for the metadata that describes the dataset. In most cases, this value will be the same as the dataset license</i>
Data license	<i>Specify here the type of data license considered. For example, open license, oDbI ...</i>
Data storage	<i>Where the data are stored</i>
Data value (long term)	<i>The expected value for the dataset, both from the project point of view and after the project lifetime (if any)</i>
Re-used data	<i>Origin of the data that is being re-used. If possible, there should be a link to a platform like Zenodo where the data has been published. Otherwise, a link to a webpage would be enough. If the re-used data is not publicly available, then a textual description of the data should be inserted.</i>
Data creation process (only for generated data)	<i>How the dataset is generated. For example, data might be collected from sensors from a particular case study, which needs to be anonymized through particular techniques.</i>
Data sample	<i>If available, a sample of the data for this dataset</i>
Related safety KPI(s)	<i>What project safety KPI(s) the dataset addresses</i>

3.2 FAIR DATA

This paragraph describes the principles adopted in EvoRoads to make the data FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Moreover, the section of the EvoRoads metadata profile used to collect FAIR data is described.

Within EvoRoads, **open access** to the data will be provided unless this is contrary to the legitimate interests of the beneficiaries, including commercial exploitation. On top of data openness, EvoRoads will fulfil the FAIR principles [1]. FAIR stands for:

- **Findable:** discoverable with metadata, identifiable, and locatable through a standard identification mechanism.
- **Accessible:** always available and obtainable; even if the data is restricted, the metadata is open. Data can be restricted and still be FAIR, following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. So not all data has to be made open. The Open Data Institute (ODI)⁸ defines Open Data as those that anyone can access, use and share. According to the ODI, Open Data must be licensed to make clear that anyone can use the data in any way they want, including transforming, combining, and sharing it with others, even for commercial purposes. On the other hand, Open Data may not be FAIR. For example, publicly available data may lack sufficient documentation to meet the FAIR principles, such as licensing for clear re-use
- **Interoperable:** both syntactically pursuable and semantically understandable, allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organizations, or countries
- **Reusable:** sufficiently described and shared with the least restrictive licenses, allowing the widest re-use possible and the least cumbersome integration with other data sources

Metadata of deposited data will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles.

⁸ <https://theodi.org/>

MAKING DATA FINDABLE

Metadata and data should be easy for both humans and computers to find. Machine-readable metadata are essential for the automatic discovery of datasets and services. Data and metadata are assigned to a globally unique and persistent identifier assigned by Cefriel for usage within the project. The published DMP will then be uniquely identified with a DOI by the Argos platform. Moreover, data are described with rich metadata that clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes.

A short description of information collected in the section “FAIR DATA - Making data Findable” is reported in Table 3.

Table 3: “FAIR DATA – Making data Findable” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

FAIR DATA – Making data findable	
Search keywords approach	<i>Indicate keywords related to the dataset</i>
Clear versioning approach (versioning and traceability) (Only for generated data)	<i>Describe here if any versioning approach is used for data and metadata, and how they are traced.</i>

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Data and metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol. This principle focuses on retrieving data and metadata from their identifiers. Data retrieval should be mediated without specialised or proprietary tools or communication methods. To maximize data re-use, the protocol should be free (no-cost) and open (-sourced) and thus globally implementable to facilitate data retrieval (e.g., HTTP, FTP, SMTP, etc.). However, where personal data is involved, the protocol must also support authentication and authorization procedures to ensure privacy and compliance with data protection regulations, such as GDPR, ensuring secure access and proper handling of sensitive information.

A short description of information collected in the section “FAIR DATA – Making data openly Accessible” is reported in Table 4.

Table 4: “FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	
Data openly available	<i>Indicate here if the data are open and free accessible (for example, specify if the protocol is free and open-sourced), or under restrictions, and, in case, specify the restrictions</i>
Data access requirements	<i>If there are any, specify the restrictions to data access, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions</i>
Data sharing method (How data will be made accessible)	<i>Describe how data will be made accessible to project partners.</i>

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Data usually needs to be integrated with other data and to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing. Interoperability typically means that each computer system has at least knowledge of the other system’s data exchange formats. (Meta)data should use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation and a controlled vocabulary. Data should be readable for machines without requiring specialized or ad hoc algorithms, translators, or mappings. Data should be collected and shared using a standard format for that data type.

A short description of information collected in the section “FAIR DATA – Making data Interoperable” is reported in Table 5.

Table 5: “FAIR DATA – Making interoperable” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	
Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	<i>Describe here if any standard or procedures for metadata creation is used, and report them</i>

INCREASE DATA RE-USE

The goal of FAIR is to optimize the re-use of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings. Therefore, (meta)data should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes and released with a clear and accessible data usage license. They should be associated with detailed provenance for enhancing data re-use, and, finally, data and metadata should meet domain-relevant community standards: if community standards or best practices for data archiving and sharing exist, they should be followed.

A short description of the information collected in “FAIR DATA Increase data-reuse” is reported in Table 6. While general fields apply to all datasets, specific fields are required only for generated data. These fields include the timing of data availability for re-use, which specifies how long the data will be accessible to others; the data's usability for third parties, ensuring that the dataset is structured and documented in a way that data can be used after the end of the project; and the length of data reusability, which outlines any data-reuse time.

Table 6: “FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	
Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo) - (Only for generated data)	<i>Indicate how long the data will be available for re-use (including embargo indications)</i>
Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project) - (Only for generated data)	<i>Describe here if the data will be available for third parties' usage, after the end of the project</i>
Restriction to data re-use	<i>Indicate here any limitations or restrictions about data and metadata re-use</i>
Quality assurance process	<i>Indicate here if you plan to indicate metrics, KPIs, or any quality assessment process. In case, provide here details</i>
Length of time of data reusability - (Only for generated data)	<i>Indicate here any data-reuse time, if it has to be defined</i>
Data licensing for wide re-use	<i>Specify here the type of data license considered for wide re-use. For example, open license, etc</i>

3.3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

This section denotes the aspects related to the allocation of resources in terms of costs and data management responsibilities.

The costs of open access to research data are eligible for the EvoRoads GA. The costs of making scientific publications and hosting a project website are included in the EvoRoads budget as eligible costs.

The Scientific and Technical Committee (STC), defined in D6.1 “Project Management Handbook”, will discuss resources for long-term preservation, associated costs and potential value, and how data will be kept beyond the project and for how long.

A short description of the information collected in the section “Allocation of resources” is reported in Table 7.

Table 7: “Allocation of resources” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
Cost estimates for making data FAIR	<i>Indicate here the estimated cost for applying the above reported FAIR principles and making data FAIR.</i>

3.4 DATA SECURITY

This section refers to the data security aspects of each dataset managed within the EvoRoads project.

Each project party is entitled to adopt its own internal policies and resources to ensure safe and secure data storage. Data storage on a safe and secure server is strongly recommended to guarantee data recovery in case of failure.

Currently, the only data storage for the EvoRoads project are the Microsoft SharePoint repository, which ERTICO made available to all partners for sharing presentations, documents, data, and deliverables, and the Mailing list server, based on open source Sympa, running on a Microsoft Azure VM.

ERTICO licenses Microsoft SharePoint, allowing for secure and controlled data sharing among the research team. Microsoft SharePoint encrypts data both in transit and at rest and is approved against ERTICO’s Handling Restricted Data Policy. SharePoint provides several layers of automatic backup, combined in the service such that the user (purchaser) need not take specific actions; files can be recovered automatically in a disaster scenario. Access to data stored in Microsoft SharePoint is via secure log-in with multi-factor authentication. Concerning data safety, ERTICO is compliant with the standard ISO 27001:2022.

ERTICO runs a Mailing list server based on open-source Sympa for distributing project emails. Project participants (un)subscribe to these mailing lists, allowing full control of their personal data within the server. Raw Data is stored on encrypted virtual disks within the Azure VM and is only reachable through SSH using a dedicated certificate provided by ERTICO’s administrator. Data is backed up automatically using the VM automatic backup and failover service.

The personnel able to access data shared among the partners involved will be agreed upon among the partners for any project task.

Further data storage repositories such as cloud servers, Github, and Zenodo could be made available for EvoRoads partners in the next months, and data security aspects will be provided for each dataset/data storage.

A short description of the information collected in the section “Data Security” is reported in Table 8.

Table 8: “Data security” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

DATA SECURITY	
Data security	<i>Describe here information about data security. For example, which servers will host the collected data, who will oversee the servers, who can access such servers, and if periodical backups are planned.</i>
Certified repositories	<i>Indicate what security measures will be implemented to guarantee safe data storage. These security measures should affect the previously indicated 'data storage'</i>

3.5 ETHICAL ASPECTS

This section refers to the ethical aspects concerning the data collected and shared within the project. All activities developed within the project will safeguard individuals' fundamental rights. During the project life cycle, the main pillars of the relevant EU legal framework will be adopted regarding ethical and legal issues.

PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA

The right to data protection is enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [3], which effectively protects individuals' right to privacy by giving them control over how information about them is collected and used. EvoRoads will pay attention to research tasks related to collecting and processing personal data (e.g., profiling, data-mining techniques, and big-data analytics) since they may pose higher risks to individuals' rights regarding data protection.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁹ will be respected for all relevant personal data collected. Proper anonymization or pseudonymization techniques will be adopted for each specific dataset that includes personal data.

Anonymization is one of the best ways to mitigate ethical concerns from using personal data [2]. However, other ethical issues could relate to the origins of the data or how they were obtained. For this reason, the source of the datasets will be clearly identified by EvoRoads to ensure that the anonymisation happens at the point and time at which the data are collected.

When the project involves the partners' access to personal data, the partners are regarded as responsible for treating said data and shall comply with the rules. The Lead Contact (LC) of each organisation involved in EvoRoads also assumes the role of Data Protection Officer (DPO).

INFORMED CONSENT PROCEDURES

Informed consent entails giving sufficient information about the research and ensuring that there is no explicit or implicit coercion so that participants in the research activities can make an informed and free decision on their possible involvement. The information must be provided in a form that is comprehensible and accessible to participants in a written form, and time should be allowed for the participants to consider their choices and to discuss their decision with others if appropriate. The informed consent must report information on the scope and objectives of the research and must inform participants of their right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the investigation whenever and for whatever reason they wish.

EvoRoads will define and adopt robust informed consent when project activities require the direct involvement of human participants. The informed consent will clearly explain how the data will be collected, used, and stored and when it will be deleted. It will clearly state that EvoRoads adopts the data minimization principle: the project collects the minimum amount of personal data needed to deliver the research activities described in the GA.

A short description of the information collected in the section "Ethical Aspects" of the EvoRoads metadata profile is reported in Table 9.

Table 9: "Ethical Aspects" section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

ETHICAL ASPECTS	
Ethical or legal issues with impact on data sharing	<i>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can impact data sharing? Does the dataset contain personal data? Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</i>

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

3.6 OTHER ISSUES

This section is meant to collect any other relevant information on the usage of other procedures for data management. A short description of the information collected in the section “Other Aspects” is reported in Table 10.

Table 10: “Other Aspects” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile.

OTHER ASPECTS	
Other procedures for data management to be specified	<i>Do you, or will you, use other national/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?</i>

4 PRELIMINARY LIST OF DATASETS

This version of the DMP aims to collect preliminary information on datasets re-used or generated by the EvoRoads project, starting from the list of datasets mentioned in the GA.

The “General Information and Data Summary” section of the EvoRoads metadata profile (see Section 3.1) has been used to start collecting the information on datasets. This minimum version of the metadata profile has been shared with the entire EvoRoads consortium. To facilitate the description and management of the datasets, Google Sheets has been chosen as the primary tool for gathering and organizing dataset descriptions, ensuring a collaborative and accessible approach for all project partners.

The minimum version of the metadata profile aims to collect the essential information without overwhelming partners with overly detailed or complex requests in the early stage of the project. In the second phase, partners must complete the entire version of the metadata profile (see Section 3) and the results will be published in the updated version of the DMP (expected at M18 and M36). This approach supports EvoRoads in gathering key information about the datasets and allows for early confirmation that the identified datasets will be used throughout the project. This ensures that detailed information, which could lead to fragmented or unnecessary submissions, is not requested in advance, especially in cases where a dataset may not be selected for use in the project.

The tables reported in this section represent the preliminary list of datasets to be managed by EvoRoads identified by project partners in this early phase of the project (M6). Each partner has been asked to make an initial identification of all the datasets collected, processed, or generated by their respective organisation during the project. Fields empty or marked as "TBD" (To Be Defined) will be filled in at a subsequent stage, once the overall dataset landscape becomes clearer and more precise information can be provided.

Cefriel assigns a unique dataset ID to each dataset during the initial data collection phase. The ID is created using a combination of three letters that represent the pilot location (ITA for Italy, SPA for the big Spanish pilot, LAT for Latvia, and ROM for Romania) or the work package (WP) number (e.g. WP2) if not part of a pilot, followed by three letters that define the category (VEH for vehicles, SAF for safety, TRA for traffic, INF for infrastructure, CON for connectivity, etc.), and a progressive number.

Table 11: Description of Dataset ITA-VEH-01

DATASET ID	ITA-VEH-01
DATASET name	Data from 2 RSUs
Description	Data from 2 Road Side Units (RSUs),
Category (Type of output)	VRU, Vehicle
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road user behavioural data, road traffic data
Partners	LINKS - Federico Princiotta, Daniele Brevi
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.3
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	The RSUs will monitor the intersections and generate live messages listing all the road actor detected and their positions. This data could be further elaborated to computed speeds and trajectories to estimate the user behaviour.
Schema of the data	CPM schema
Format of the data	CPM, in Json format
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	

DATASET ID	ITA-VEH-01
DATASET name	Data from 2 RSUs
Data storage	
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Process camera and lidar data to generate CPM messages.
Data sample	

Table 12: Description of Dataset ITA-INF-01

DATASET ID	ITA-INF-01
DATASET name	Data from road infrastructure
Description	Data from Road Infrastructure digital twin
Category (Type of output)	Infrastructure
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road maintenance data, road traffic data
Partners	LINKS - Federico Princiotta, Daniele Brevi
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T3.1, T4.3
Work packages	WP3, WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	The digital twin will collect data from all the sensors in Turin available during the project and provide access to them.
Schema of the data	CPM/CAM/DENM schemas
Format of the data	CPM, CAM, DENM, in Json format
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	
Data sample	

Table 13: Description of Dataset ITA-TRA-01

DATASET ID	ITA-TRA-01
DATASET name	Road Accident dataset 2000
Description	Road Accident dataset (no. injured or dead persons, time, position, etc.), available from 2000
Category (Type of output)	Traffic
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road accident data
Partners	LINKS - Andrea Ballocca, Marina Dragonieri
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.3

DATASET ID	ITA-TRA-01
DATASET name	Road Accident dataset 2000
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Historical DB of road accident, which could be used to look for correlation between safety KPI and actual accident severity/frequency
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	TBC (Json, CVS, XML)
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	TBC
Data storage	
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Historical Data
Data sample	

Table 14: Description of Dataset ITA-TRA-02

DATASET ID	ITA-TRA-02
DATASET name	Road traffic data
Description	Road traffic data (avg. daily traffic flow, link to the regional road graph) available from 2014 to 2022
Category (Type of output)	Traffic
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road traffic data
Partners	LINKS - Andrea Ballocca, Marina Dragonieri
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.3
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Historical DB of road traffic flow, which could be used to look for correlation between traffic and actual accidents severity/frequency.
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	TBC (Json, CVS, XML)
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	TBC
Data storage	
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Historical Data.
Data sample	

Table 15: Description of Dataset SPA-INF-01

DATASET ID	SPA-INF-01
DATASET name	Data from vehicles through 5G network
Description	Connected vehicle data: Data from vehicles through 5G network
Category (Type of output)	Infrastructure
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Vehicle sensor data, connectivity network data
Partners	INDRA
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.2
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Receiving information from vehicles via 5G. Metrics on received data volumes and upload speeds
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	CAM/DENM/CPM
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	TBC (Server/cloud)
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Associate IDs with the data of each vehicle on a given stretch of road
Data sample	

Table 16: Description of Dataset SPA-VEH-01

DATASET ID	SPA-VEH-01
DATASET name	Road status data
Description	Road status data: Data from on-board sensors regarding accelerometers, etc.
Category (Type of output)	Vehicle
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Vehicle sensor data
Partners	INDRA
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.2
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Vehicle vibration values that allow road conditions to be extrapolated and the areas with the most defects to be identified
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	TBC (Json, CVS, XML)
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	TBC (Server/cloud)

DATASET ID	SPA-VEH-01
DATASET name	Road status data
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Data filtering to remove noise and extreme outliers.
Data sample	

Table 17: Description of Dataset SPA-INF-02

DATASET ID	SPA-INF-02
DATASET name	Road Infrastructure Digital twin data
Description	Road Infrastructure Digital twin data: Platform visualization of data over a Digital Twin of the road
Category (Type of output)	Infrastructure
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road defects data
Partners	INDRA
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.2
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Near real-time knowledge of road conditions for a specific section of road
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	TBC (Server/cloud)
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Visual representation of the road status through 2D/3D GIS based model
Data sample	

Table 18: Description of Dataset LAT-VRU-01

DATASET ID	LAT-VRU-01
DATASET name	OBU and OAK-D cameras
Description	On-Board Units (OBU) and OAK-D cameras (capture 3D depth infra information)
Category (Type of output)	VRU
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road defect data
Partners	DOTS - Riga
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T3.5, T4.4

DATASET ID	LAT-VRU-01
DATASET name	OBU and OAK-D cameras
Work packages	WP3, WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	The VRU mounted kit will collect data from camera (AI driven detection of road quality)
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	TBC (Json, XML, Image)
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	
Data sample	

Table 19: Description of Dataset LAT-VRU-01

DATASET ID	LAT-VRU-02
DATASET name	On-Board Units
Description	On-Board Units (OBU)
Category (Type of output)	VRU
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Vehicle sensor data
Partners	DOTS - Riga
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T3.5, T4.4
Work packages	WP3, WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	The VRU mounted kit will collect data from sensors
Schema of the data	
Format of the data	TBC (Json, XML)
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	
Data sample	

Table 20: Description of Dataset WP2-INF-01

DATASET ID	WP2-INF-01
DATASET name	2D Visual Data
Description	Road safety and infrastructure condition data

DATASET ID	WP2-INF-01
DATASET name	2D Visual Data
Category (Type of output)	Infrastructure, Drones, Traffic
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road infrastructure data, Road defects data, Road Traffic data
Partners	UCY
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	TBD
Work packages	WP2
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Infrastructure monitoring
Schema of the data	Description of imaging information
Format of the data	.jpg, .png, mp4
Size	1-100s GB
Dataset metadata license	CC-BY
Data license	TBD
Data storage	Server
Data value (long term)	-
Re-used data	Possible
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Footage capture from drone camera
Data sample	Image/Video data

Table 21: Description of Dataset WP2-INF-02

DATASET ID	WP2-INF-02
DATASET name	Road safety and infrastructure condition image
Description	Road safety and infrastructure condition data
Category (Type of output)	Infrastructure, Crowdsourcing data, Safety
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Asset management and road maintenance data, Road infrastructure data, Road defects data, Roadside units data, Crowdsourcing data
Partners	UCY
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	TBD
Work packages	WP2
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Infrastructure monitoring for safety reasons
Schema of the data	Description of imaging information
Format of the data	.jpg, .png, mp4
Size	-
Dataset metadata license	TBD
Data license	CC-BY
Data storage	Server
Data value (long term)	-
Re-used data	Possible
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Footage capture from smartphone camera
Data sample	Image data

Table 22: Description of Dataset WP2-INF-03

DATASET ID	WP2-INF-03
DATASET name	Road safety and infrastructure condition table data
Description	Road safety and infrastructure condition data
Category (Type of output)	Infrastructure, Crowdsourcing data, Safety
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Asset management and road maintenance data, Road infrastructure data, Road defects data, Roadside units data, Crowdsourcing data
Partners	UCY
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	TBD
Work packages	WP2
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Infrastructure monitoring for safety reasons
Schema of the data	Description of tabular data information
Format of the data	xls, csv
Size	-
Dataset metadata license	TBD
Data license	CC-BY
Data storage	Server
Data value (long term)	-
Re-used data	Possible
Data creation process (only for generated data)	-
Data sample	Table data

Table 23: Description of Dataset WP2-CON-01

DATASET ID	WP2-CON-01
DATASET name	Env_Sensor.db, RoadStatus.db, AtmRoad_info.db, transito.db, Asphalt_temp.db, Camera.db
Description	Environmental conditions (Temperature & Humidity), asphalt Temperature, Fog condition, Object detections informations vehicules related to the road line location, information about if the road is obstructed or not
Category (Type of output)	Connectivity
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Road status data
Partners	EUT - Arcadi Castanyer, Jesus David Coral
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	
Work packages	WP2
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Producing information of the environmental and road condition
Schema of the data	Description of tabular data information
Format of the data	InnoDB
Size	1 - 50 GB
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	GPL

DATASET ID	WP2-CON-01
DATASET name	Env_Sensor.db, RoadStatus.db, AtmRoad_info.db, transito.db, Asphalt_temp.db, Camera.db
Data storage	Server
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Data collected from sensor. Temperature sensor Humidity sensor Ultrasonic sensor Camera sensor Luminosity sensor Infrared sensor
Data sample	Table data / Image data

Table 24: Description of Dataset WP4-VEH-01

DATASET ID	WP4-VEH-01
DATASET name	Connected vehicle data
Description	Connected vehicle data: Data from EDGE to Vehicles via 5G
Category (Type of output)	Vehicle
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	C-ITS data about road status data
Partners	IDIADA - Jacint Castells
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.2
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Receiving information from the infrastructure via 5G to warn the vehicles/drivers
Schema of the data	Data for Road Safety schema
Format of the data	DATEX II Data for Road Safety
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	TBC (Server/cloud)
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Process infrastructure sensors' data and generate the C-ITS messages accordingly
Data sample	

Table 25: Description of Dataset WP4-CON-01

DATASET ID	WP4-CON-01
DATASET name	Scores and parameters from probe and maintenance vehicles
Description	Map with scores and parameters obtained and processed via connectivity information from probe and maintenance vehicles
Category (Type of output)	Connectivity

DATASET ID	WP4-CON-01
DATASET name	Scores and parameters from probe and maintenance vehicles
Data requirement (Data availability and data sources)	Connectivity network data
Partners	CTAG - Aitor González
RELATION TO THE PROJECT	
Workstream	T4.2
Work packages	WP4
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the data	Support vehicles to make decisions (safety oriented) based on such quality of service of existing connectivity
Schema of the data	TBC
Format of the data	TBC
Size	
Dataset metadata license	
Data license	
Data storage	TBV
Data value (long term)	
Re-used data	
Data creation process (only for generated data)	Own connectivity coverage analysis tool
Data sample	

5 CONCLUSION

In this first release of the Data Management Plan for the EvoRoads project, we have established a foundational framework for data management. While we have identified and documented datasets collected by each partner organization, we recognize that the DMP is a living document that will evolve as the project progresses and more datasets are collected.

As the project unfolds, we will continue to review and update the DMP to reflect evolving project needs, technological advancements, and regulatory requirements.

In summary, the DMP serves as a roadmap for responsible and ethical data management practices, laying the groundwork for collaboration, innovation, and knowledge exchange within the research community. We remain dedicated to fostering a culture of openness, transparency, and accountability in the management and use of research data, while also respecting the privacy concerns associated with specific EvoRoads pilots.

6 REFERENCES

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